

Impulse Buying Behavior and the Role of Social Media: A Case Study of Faisalabad

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Abstract:

Purchasing a product without planning is termed as impulse buying. In the busy rapidly changing life of this time, people usually do impulse buying that is why now marketing experts are paying attention to catch the impulse of window shoppers. Researchers have proved that impulse buying has become a significant part of marketing studies. Now different marketing experts are focusing on finding different factors affecting impulse buying. Present study is a modest effort towards this concern. Present study focused on finding the determinants of impulse buying of the consumers in Faisalabad city with a special focus on the role that social media is playing in generating impulse buying behavior of window shoppers. Primary data were collected from 120 respondents, selected randomly. Data were collected using fully structured questionnaire. Both descriptive and inferential analyses were carried out. The major econometric analysis was done by multiple regressions. Regression was estimated through the method of ordinary least square for impulse buying as a function of marketing and personal factors of consumers. The results revealed that social media would be a good tool for increasing the impulse buying in Faisalabad. Results further showed that family income, education, gender, age, promotional activities, display of a store, behavior of the sales person and social media contribute positively in enhancing the impulse buying. So, it can be recommended that the sellers should consider these factors while making their policies.

Keywords: Impulse Buying, Social Media, Promotional Activities.

1- INTRODUCTION

An impulse buying or purchasing means unplanned shopping or spontaneous purchase. When a consumer sees any new product, well-established or sample products at surprisingly low prices, he tends to show impulse behavior. Parboteeah (2005) and Piron (1991) defined that impulse purchases were the result of an exposure to a stimulus causes unplanned buying, and this phenomenon involves on the spot decision by the shopper. An Impulse buyer begins browsing without having any intention to buy a certain thing while visiting a certain store. As buyers browse, they are exposed to the stimuli, which incites customers' urge to impulse buy. When impulse buyer feels the desire to buy, he/she makes a purchase decision without searching for information or evaluating alternatives. However, buyers may experience a positive or negative consequence by the post-purchase evaluation after he buys on impulse. In the whole process, there are many factors which influence the consumers by triggering their impulse purchase behavior.

Social media has appeared as a useful device in present marketing system. It is experimental that all institute whether commercial or non-commercial are using social media for their gratitude. Marketing through social media is a networking that is relating and appealing the people in conversations. People do relate and contribute to their views, culture and life style all the way through social media. Social media is a mechanism in hovering new ideas. This exciting aspect of social media has fascinated many researchers and businessmen. Every entrepreneur is using social media as a good marketing instrument (O'Reilly, 2005). Basically, marketing through social media is a pioneering mode to draw contemporary customers towards the apprehensive product. Nowadays almost all good businessmen are encouraging their product/ services via social media, because social media is an axis of interest for working age group ((Boyd and Ellison, 2007).

There are many factors that can influence the impulse purchasing activities of the people such as demographic, economic, cultural and social factors etc. Demographics factors such as age and gender, channel awareness, apparent circulation utility, and supposed availability are vigorous forecasters of Internet users' online purchasing position (Li *et al.*, 1999). The accessibility of 24-hour retailing via the internet had brought about an enhancement in online retailing and this critical, an escalation in impulsive purchasing (Eroglu *et al.*, 2001). By means of the propagation of E-commerce, it is raising indication that online impulsive purchasing is an evolving occurrence, which has become the focal point of scholars from a diversity of directions (Wells *et al.*, 2011). It is moment for the companies to formulate operative approaches and accomplish them to prevail bigger part of trade all the way through this radical medium and develop into the advanced firm of upcoming future (Bashar *et al.*, 2012). It has been observed that not all impulse buying is the same. While the purchase of an item may have not been planned for a specific shopping trip, it does not automatically mean that is not needed or not previously considered. "The effects of sales promotion strategy, product appeal and consumer traits on reminder impulse buying behavior," the research specifically analyze purchases that were not planned, but when seeing a certain item the customer recalls that they need it.

In addition, the interaction effect of sales promotion strategy and consumer traits on reminder impulse buying is significant. "Hedonic consumers prefer nonmonetary-based promotion over monetary-based promotions, but there is no significant difference between the two kinds of promotions for prudent consumers" (Chia-Hsien and Lindquist, 2009). Knowledge gained from this article can help marketers understand how to categorize products and as a result how to best promote them towards either reminder impulse buyers or pure impulse buyers. Another article looks at how the store image impacts impulse buying. The authors of the "Role of store image in consumer impulse buying behavior" article noticed that some retailers in India were focused on improving store image, while others were focusing on low prices. With these observations they wanted to see which one is the better driver for impulse purchases.

They investigated buyers at a shopping place about the practices and “measured store image through its layout, music, employee friendliness and lighting” (Sivakumaran and Sharma, 2009).

Furthermore, technology allows marketers to apply innovative new ways to reach people and decrease the transaction time to make impulse purchases truly impulsive. Several inventive companies are described how television infomercial companies are also seeing the value of impulse buying through the internet and are developing technologies to expedite the purchasing process. Infomercials’ whole business is built on impulse purchases by reaching out to people where they are and showing them the benefits of a particular product. “We’re placing a big bet on that the industry that we think is in need of innovation,” (Verhagen, and Van 2011). These companies know that their tactic now needs to include a more aggressive Internet strategy to continue to reach out to people in their own environment. The goal for the inclusion of these web-based technologies is get transactions processed faster, while customers still have that initial impulse and before they going through a decision making process. If we have an opportunity for them to see a commercial and to react that quickly, the chances for us to make a sale increase dramatically,’ said Kevin Vick, a partner with Boston Ideas”. These technologies allow consumers to see a product, be amazed by it, and purchase it in a very short amount of time. To increase sales, these companies are trying to continually reduce that amount of time where a customer might rethink a purchase and decide against it. Sonia Makurdsik, marketing consultant for Hampton Direct, sums up the new online strategy of these companies by saying, “Flipping through the channel is not enough. Your brand message needs to be present wherever the consumer is” (Verhagen, and Van 2011).

So it is important for entrepreneurs / businessmen to know the evolving behavior of consumers that is impulse buying or unplanned shopping. The study in hand will look into impulse buying behavior, its trends and role of communication technology means especially social media in promoting this behavior.

Faisalabad is now one of the leading users of information and communication technologies among all cities of Pakistan. This research is focused on exploring that how social media is playing its role in consumers’ consumption pattern in Faisalabad. As per the requirement of time the people are much busy and has set the purchasing planning on “no planning” (This no planning purchasing is called impulse buying explained earlier). People do see the new emerging trendy items on social media and have images of all these items in their mind somewhere. These images stimulate them in purchasing similar things at first glance while doing window shopping. This study is focused on exploring that how this social media is affecting the impulse buying behavior of Faisalabad’s consumers.

This study is conducted in Faisalabad City with the following objectives:

- To identify the factors affecting the impulse buying behavior of consumers.
- To investigate the role of social media in consumer impulse buying behavior.

This research study provides a deep understanding of variables and investigates inter-relationships between impulse buying behavior and role of social media: a case study of Faisalabad city. The importance of triggers when carrying out an impulse purchase. Model of study also investigates consumers feel that the product is good value for money. Consumers are easily attracted by social media and the opportunity to make a bargain.

2- LITERATURE REVIEW

Zafar and Wong (1993) investigated that it was essential to have an actual striking inner atmosphere of the store. Variables those influence the customers more in the inner side of the store those were musical atmosphere, whole presentation, trained well staff, promotion strategies, pricing strategies sanitation of shop and wide space played an important part in impulse purchasing. Categorically the shopping in the inner atmosphere was having two different effect of in store point of buying, picture on customers, urging he attitude in location of superstore.

Petty (1998) studied impulse buying conduct and part of online networking. The objective of this study was to examine how these social impacts through interpersonal organization locales influence individuals' general demeanor towards item, when they share or talk about the insights about the item and how this can impact Impulse buying propensity. This could be conceivable just on the off chance that we can survey how the informal community groups can practice impact on shopper's subjective procedure included in assessing the manner towards the item that is being examined by the part and how the basic attributes of these interpersonal organization locales can influence the influence process and there by influence the rash purchasing tendency. The aforementioned changes in interest towards an item can enormously be roused by interpersonal impact.

Li *et al.*, (1999) anticipated and experienced a customer online purchasing behavior model. The model posited that customer online purchasing attitude was influenced by demographics, channel utilities supposed, channel information, and shopping orientations. Data were collected by a research company employing an online survey of 999 U.S. internet users, and were cross-confirmed with other related national surveys. Findings indicated that education; convenience orientation, experience orientation, channel knowledge, perceived distribution utility, and perceived accessibility were vigorous antecedents of online buying status.

Dholakia (2000) analyzed that impulse buying was ever-present and exceptional aspect of life style of consumers. Retailers realized the value of this happening through product packaging, store's promotions and layouts. They had tried to search out impulsiveness of consumers in stores.

Eroglu *et al.*, (2001) explored researchers from multiple areas, such as consumer behavior and psychology. Swift growth in IT had significantly distorted the surroundings of consumer behavior in the preceding decade. The accessibility of 24-hour transaction through the internet had convinced enrichment in online transaction and this essential; enlarge in impulse buying. Through an increased accessibility to products and services with the Internet, consumers' buying opportunities had extended and it gave ease to make purchases. Anyhow, this latest shopping mode frequently eradicated the time restrictions and gap that are practiced by shoppers often in a predictable trade circumstance.

Wong (2003) studied that sometimes impulsiveness depends on the store. Price of the product is a different variable of impulse purchasing. Customers become more impulsive when there are product discounts or sales, short life of the product, smaller sizes, less marginal need for the product and ease of storage.

Crawford and Melewar, (2003) found that the marketers should sponsor a good store design to increase the accessibility of the customers. A very well-trained sales representative could lessen the hindrance by managing and assisting the customers in the buying procedure and trigger impulsive purchasing attitude. Store conditions were significant to convince impulse buying. Store executives could see many of environmental scheme factors to enhance stimuli in their shops. Sometimes impulsiveness depends on the type of the store.

Mai and Willett (2003) investigated that the availability of cash was an expediter in the process of impulsive buying. Though it enhanced the buying capacity of the individual. If the individual did not have much cash, he/ she would reluctant the buying environment. Customers had tendency to purchase impulsively. Internet explorer persons usually made more impulsive buying are than who did not use the internet explorer.

Wong and Zhou (2003) explored that the price of the product was new variable of impulsive purchasing. Customer's intentions to be much impulsive when there were product discounts or sales promotions. Less minimal requirements for the product, less item life, small in sizes and availability of stores. If the product would be purchased on an impulse buying rely on the category of the product. It was observed that impulsive purchasing happened more in the occasion of hedonic items due to the convey of symbolic meaning.

Sreedhar *et al.*, (2004) explored another remarkable study to conceptualize the impulse buying conduct. In the study they investigated the idea of "Presentation to Stimulus" in point of interest and is increased to incorporate boosts other than the item itself (real research amid this time were just accept the item as the main stimulus). According to them the item is not by any means the only stimuli and expect that just physical nearness prompts impulsive buying, all things considered it neglects to record for motivation buys on the Internet. Their discoveries recommend that impulse buying exists on the Internet, and there is "stimulus other than the item", that cause the possible motivation buys. They likewise tried the variables, for example, in-store perusing and disposition states and discovered these variables impact impulsive buying on the web. In the study they likewise found that the air signals and positive hedonic encounters additionally impact the impulse buys on the web.

Parboteeah (2005) examined online setting of impulse buying behavior. They suggested a hypothetical model to explicate such behavior in an e-commerce situation. Results of this study proposed that two situations boost up impulse purchase behavior in online setting. First, any unconstructive cognitive responses should be condensed by certifying that the website is safe and sound and trouble-free to navigate. Second, the easy-to-read reactions to the boundary should be made as greater as possible by using a sophisticated and ingenious interface design.

Rundh (2005) investigated that the most of customers were overstated by inner environmental factors in Impulse behavior of customer. Impulsive purchasing of customers was generally due "the stimulus". Advertisers be a concentrate for the thought of customers for impulse purchasing through promotion stimuli outer factors, when customers "displaying stimulus as advertising inducement". The retail arrangements of store were affecting the feedback of the customers for in store and future store decisions as well. The condition of the store and physical presence effects on customers' choice for choosing a store.

Walsh (2006) discovered an informal organization locale including Myspace and Facebook was a main impetus behind expanding volume of activity to retail destinations. This increment in activity from informal community locales to online retailers demonstrates that exceedingly persuasive clients straight forwardly influence other customers' choice making. Social influence was vital in buy choices that were arranged too us motivation could be because of the way shoppers see the believability of the source and continuous correspondence plausibility with the source.

Wells *et al.*, (2007) investigated that the higher income level was one of several variables, which accounted for modified step of impulse buying in comparison with America and many countries of the universe. The impulsive purchasing was established as a larger for the customers who could have enough money. The income level strongly effect on customers impulse buying attitude. Customer who wanted to purchase the items was dependent on their income. The customers with more income level were lesser complex than customers with low income and customers with more income would often include into impulse buy.

Hung (2008) investigated on consumer impulse buying behavior. Demographic data was collected. For the reliability of data researcher used Cronbach's Alpha method. Five factors were indicated environmental, situational, advertisement, promotion and customer impulse buying tendencies. He also concentrated on female customer impulsive purchasing attitude in ecommerce environment. In this study, the investigator gathered the data regarding demographic variables. In his study he used survey method. He used Cronbach's Alpha for the measurement of data reliability. In his study, he specified above mentioned demographic variables. All the variables contributed to affect the attitude of ladies in online impulsive purchasing except advertising and promotion.

Maikstieniene and Auruskeviciene (2008) investigated about the window display in relations of consumer's purchasing habits had a less priority. Hence, the presentation of the store affects customer's top importance. The visible level creates the top importance. It could recommend that it may affect the customers at certain level. Currently it was bigger the status of "window display" to appeal the attention and finally to change the people into the purchasers.

Rita (2009) studied that if the marketing activities those were placed and accurate by the marketer in effort to incentive customers into impulsive purchasing attitude. Customers' could practice an impulsive to insensitively gaining when visually come across stimulates such as promotional activities. External marketing stimulates attract fresh consumers into a selling through web site, but stimulate straight selling to existing consumers by promising impulsive buying of courtesy products or improved products. The condition and retail situation were the causes, which affects the feedback and store type reason of supposing nature of expectation, subjectivity and presentation.

Karbasivar and Yarahmadi (2011) tried to get the factors/ variables those change customer impulse purchasing attitude. Data was collected from Abdan, Iran and researchers used survey research method with sample size of 275 respondents. The value of Cronbach's Alpha was calculated to confirm the trustworthiness of data. To test the variables/factors, the researchers developed a structure equation model (SEM) with linear structural relationships (LISREL). Results showed that cash discount and window display affected the impulse buying behavior more as compared to credit card and free products.

Alireza & Hasti (2011) studied that window displays in retail businesses were experiencing massive development globally just due to change in customers choices, use pattern, taste and buying, each retail store was convincing to retain and to sell their items and grip "the strong strategic opportunities of the promotional mix activities". Furthermore purposed that window display was relating with customer's buying behavior had physical charm and attraction of a store affecting consumer's choices of a store."

Bashar *et al.*, (2012) studied the efficiency of social media as a marketing tool and a great effort had been made to study the degree of social media helps consumers in making buying decision. Various statistical tests had been applied to support the research hypothesis. They advised that it was moment for the companies to formulate operative approaches and accomplish them to prevail larger share of business all the way through this innovative medium and develop into the advanced firm of upcoming future

Dipta (2012) examined relationship between the decision of online impulse purchasing and impulse consumption through online purchasing frequently. The data was from 104 respondents who were having different backgrounds, then analyzed by using mediating and moderated regression analysis. The relationship was moderated between the decision of online impulse purchasing and impulse consumption through online purchasing frequently.

3- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aims at determining the factors shaping impulse buying behavior of the customers in the actual markets. The study is conducted in Faisalabad city which is the third largest city of Pakistan. The internet accessibility in Faisalabad is growing and hence internet users, which provides opportunity to the companies to use social media as an effective marketing tool. Many leading brands of clothing, foot ware, accessories, automobiles, cellular phones have their social media web pages which motivate consumers to make an impulse purchase. For example while visiting face book or browsing internet you see some advertisements are impressed and buy. Moreover, social media is influencing the buying behavior of consumers as one consumer sees lots of pictures and posts of colleagues and friends on social media and is motivated to shop things in real market just because of those posts and pictures.

Data Collection

First-hand information from the respondents is obtained through a well-developed questionnaire. The questions are asked from the respondents relevant to the study objectives. Both Likert and nominal scales are used to get meaningful and detailed information. Random sampling technique is employed to draw the samples for the study. Before starting full-scale data collection activity pre-testing on 25 respondents was carried out to examine the workability and sensitivity of the questionnaire. In order to enhance the scope of study maximum variation is captured in urban areas of the district through selecting all the four urban towns. Total of 30 respondents were drawn randomly from each town and hence sample size of the study is 120.

Conceptual Framework

The responses are gathered from quantitative way

Through a well-developed measuring instrument and also through qualitative method, a direct focus group interview is conducted with various respondents. Cross-sectional study was conducted to examine the effect of socio-economic, cultural, demographic and nutritional characteristics of the respondents on impulse buying behavior.

Data Analysis

Multiple regression model was executed to analyze the collected data and to fulfill the study objective. The functional of the model seems as below:

IBB = F (age, family income, Behavior of sales person, Display of a store, Education, Social Media, promotional activities, time spent on social media, gender.)

$$IBB = F (A, FI, BSP, DS, EDU, SM, PA, TS, G)$$

IBB = Impulse Buying Behavior.

A = Age of the Respondent

FI = Total Family Income of the respondent households

BSP = Behavior of a Sales Person with a respondent

DS = Display of a Store which attracts to consumer

EDU = Education of the respondent

SM = Social Media which a respondent Use.

PA = Promotional Activities which affect consumer

TS = Time spend on social media by a respondent

G = Gender of the respondent

Variable Name	Recording Method
IBB (Impulse Buying Behavior)	Recorded in both Nominal and Likert scale
Family Income	Sum of income of all family members
Display of a store	Display of store which attracts shoppers in both Nominal and Likert scale
Behavior of Sales Person	Recorded in both Nominal and Likert scale
Education	Education of the respondent
Social Media	Recorded in both Nominal and Likert scale
Age	Age of the respondent
Promotional Activities	Recorded in both Nominal and Likert scale
Time Spend on Social Media	Recorded in both Nominal and Likert scale
Gender	Recorded in both Nominal scale

Multiple Regression model is used in this study to examine the effects of socio-economic factors, Demographic Factors, Personal Factors, Psychological Factors and internet usage on impulse buying of shoppers in Faisalabad. The model is estimated through the

method of ordinary least square (OLS). Dependent variable is in continuous form that's why we used OLS. OLS minimizes the sum of square of residuals and makes the estimations as closer to reality as possible. The estimated coefficients of regression need two things to be explain. Firstly, the sign of the coefficient either positive or negative. Positive sign means that dependent variable can increases with increase in independent variable being discussed. And negative sign means that dependent variable decreases with increase in independent variable being discussed. Secondly, after checking the sign of coefficient, the magnitude of the coefficient is to be interpreted.

The magnitude of coefficient tells that how much dependent variable is expected to be changed with increase in independent variable whose coefficient is being explained.

Multiple Regression Model

In order to determine the predictive power of age, family income, behavior of sales person, display of a store, education, social media, promotional activities, time spent on social media, gender used for IBB, multiple regression analysis was performed. The results are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of the Estimated Model

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.035	.543		.064	.949
Family Income (FI)	0.0042	.000	.086	1.784	.077
Education (EDU)	1.173	.111	.594	10.548	.000
Gender (G)	-.131	.223	-.027	-5.89	.557
Age (A)	.002	.008	.011	.231	.818
Promotional Activities (PA)	.023	.012	.108	1.937	.055
Display of a Store (DS)	.041	.021	.104	1.923	.057
Behavior of Sales Person (BSP)	.219	.099	.100	2.211	.029
Social Media (SM)	.014	.006	.121	2.164	.033
Time Spend on Social Media (TSM)	.078	.062	.060	1.255	.212
R Square	= 0.813		F Ratio	= 53.239	
Adjusted R Square	= 0.798		Significance	= 0.000	

Source: Author's Calculations

4- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows significant relationship of family income and impulse buying behavior at 10% level of significance. Results of regression model reveals that impulse buying can be increased by 0.086 units with the per unit increase in income of a family while the affect of other variables held constant. Education plays very most significant role in generating impulse buying behavior at 0.000 P-value as shown in Table 1. Per unit increase in education can cause an increase in impulse buying behavior by 0.594 units while the affect of other independent factors kept constant. Gender and age are non-significant variables according to the results of the study. Promotional activities and display of a store are significantly associated with generating impulse buying behavior at 10% significance level. Per unit increase in promotional activities can increase 0.108 units of impulse buying behavior whilst the affect of other factors remain unchanged. Whereas 0.104 units of impulse buying behavior can be boost up with the unit increases in display of a store while the affect of other variables held constant. Results indicate significant effect of sales person's behavior on shoppers' impulse buying behavior at 5% level of significance. Furthermore, Table 1 shows very effective role of social media in triggering impulse buying behavior of a shopper at 5% level of significance. Results shows per unit increase in social media can increase 0.1 units of impulse buying behavior whilst the affect of other factors remain unchanged. Results of regression model reveal that the time spending on social media doesn't have significant effect on impulse buying behavior.

Moreover, Table 1 depicts adjusted R square that is coefficient of determinant of Impulse buying behavior (IBB) with Family Income (FI), Education (EDU), Gender (G), Age (A), Promotional Activities (PA), and Display of a Store (DS), Behavior of Sales Person (BSP), Social Media (SM), and Time Spend on Social Media (TSM). The adjusted R^2 is 79.8% indicates that 79.8% of the total variability in IBB can be explained by FI, EDU, G, A, PA, DS, BSP, SM and TSM. Whereas remaining 20.2% variations in IBB is due to the factors that are not included in the study. Moreover the model summary also shown the overall significant relationship of family income, education, gender, age, promotional activities, display of a store, behavior of sales person, social media and time spend on a social media with impulse buying behavior at $P=0.000$.

5-CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Present study shows that display of a store and impulse buying behavior has positive effect. It may influence the shoppers while purchasing and it can affect their decisions. Sellers should decorate their display points as attractive as possible, should offer charming promotional activities and well trained staff as well. The positive and significant association between education and impulse buying behavior is seen in this study. Behavior of sales person is an external factor which causes of impulse buying of the shoppers. The results of our study show that there is a positive relationship between behavior of a sales person and impulse buying. So it is recommended that the sales person should behave politely and nicely with customers.

Most of the consumers are observed as active users of social media during the survey conduction. Entrepreneurs are advised to promote their products through social media and should provide proper and detailed description of their products. The entrepreneurs of Faisalabad should be acknowledged about the importance of such factors. They should be provided with the importance of social media as a powerful marketing tool. As the role of social media found to be effective in boosting up the impulse buying so the brands should try to be prominent in social media through proper advertisement.

There is major problem of choice in this era of global village. Businessmen should present their products in distinguished way to attract impulse buyers. The basic factors in artificial distension may the better way of advertisement. Location and decoration are much important factors in attracting the attention of the consumers. The location should be some very decent area of the city with high income groups as most of the impulse buyers are observed having high level of income.

Promotional activities such as buy-one get-one free, discount offers etc. significantly and positively contribute towards impulse buying behavior of shoppers in Faisalabad city. The reason could be that promotional activities create stimuli to shoppers which incite them to shop impulsively. So the entrepreneurs should offer good promotional packages keeping their cost benefits analysis functional. More the variety more the attention taken from consumers is a basic rule of marketing. Entrepreneurs should invest more to present more variety to consumer so that they will be more attracted towards their shops.

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